

A Binary Logistic Regression Model For Assessing The Determinants of Postharvest Losses of Plantain Among Retail Traders in Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the determinants of postharvest losses (PHL) of plantains among retail traders in Benue State, Nigeria. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 250 respondents across four local government areas: Buruku, Gboko, Makurdi, and Otuokpo. Data were collected using standardized structured questionnaires. The socio-demographic analysis revealed that the majority of respondents were female 197(78.8%), with most 108 (43.2%) aged between 31-40 years. A significant proportion of traders had primary 74(29.6%) or secondary education 98(39.2%). Most respondents 140(56%) had trading experience ranging from 1-10 years, and the majority 156(62.4%) were married. On average, plantain traders reported losses of approximately 34 bunches per trading season, equivalent to an income loss of about ₦254,000, with 68% of these losses occurring during storage. The binary logistic regression analysis identified several factors associated with postharvest losses. Factors reducing the likelihood of losses included the trader's age (odds = 0.855, $p = 0.009$), educational level (odds = 0.831, $p = 0.007$), years of trading experience (odds = 0.885, $p = 0.005$), transport availability (odds = 0.418, $p = 0.002$), market availability (odds = 0.586, $p = 0.000$), storage availability (odds = 0.698, $p = 0.001$), and membership in a trading organization (odds = 0.768, $p = 0.019$). Conversely, factors increasing the likelihood of postharvest losses of plantain included storage duration (odds = 2.625, $p = 0.000$), quantity of plantains purchased (odds = 4.933, $p = 0.000$), distance from the point of purchase (odds = 3.721, $p = 0.000$), and plantain variety (odds = 2.396, $p = 0.008$). These findings suggest that inadequate storage facilities, transportation challenges, handling limitations, and the processing of large quantities of plantain contribute significantly to postharvest losses. To reduce postharvest losses of plantains in Benue State, the study recommends that stakeholders should prioritize improving storage and transportation infrastructure, providing trader training, enhancing market access, supporting trading

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associations, implementing policy interventions, addressing high-risk factors, and investing in research and development for sustainable solutions.

Keywords: Logistic Regression, Postharvest Losses, Plantain, Retail Traders, Benue State, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Postharvest losses (PHL) refer to the reduction in quantity and quality of agricultural produce between harvest and consumption. These losses are a significant concern, particularly in developing countries, where inadequate storage facilities, inefficient transportation systems, and poor handling practices are common (FAO, 2017). In Nigeria, postharvest losses are a pervasive issue that negatively affects food security, income, and the overall agricultural economy. Plantain, a staple crop grown in several regions of Nigeria, is highly susceptible to such losses, particularly during storage and transportation. Retail traders who play a key role in the marketing and distribution of plantains often face challenges that lead to substantial losses in both quantity and quality of the crop. Addressing these issues is crucial for improving food security and enhancing the livelihoods of small-scale traders and farmers.

In Benue State, located in the central region of Nigeria, plantain farming is a major agricultural activity, with the crop being produced predominantly by smallholder farmers. However, the postharvest losses of plantain in the state are considerable, primarily due to inadequate storage infrastructure, poor transportation networks, and inadequate knowledge of postharvest management among traders (Adisa & Ogunbameru, 2019). As a result, plantains are often wasted, particularly due to rapid ripening and spoilage, which not only affects the supply chain but also results in significant economic losses. The challenges faced by traders in Benue State provide an ideal case for investigating the factors contributing to these postharvest losses and formulating strategies for their reduction.

Several studies have explored the causes of postharvest losses in various agricultural commodities. In the context of plantains, losses can be attributed to various factors including improper handling, lack of adequate storage facilities, and long transportation distances, which increase the chances of physical damage and spoilage (Adeoye *et al.*, 2017; Olorunda & Afolabi, 2018). Additionally, socio-economic factors such as the trader's age, education level, and market experience have been found to influence the likelihood of postharvest losses (Ikenna *et al.*, 2015). In Benue State, while there is an understanding of these factors, few studies have used statistical models to quantify their effects and determine the most significant predictors of postharvest losses among retail traders.

Binary logistic regression, a statistical method used to model the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables, is an appropriate tool for understanding the factors that contribute to postharvest losses in plantain retail trade. This model

allows for the assessment of both continuous and categorical predictors, making it suitable for evaluating the complex interplay between various socio-economic, logistical, and environmental factors that influence postharvest losses. Logistic regression has been successfully applied in agricultural studies to assess the impact of different variables on production outcomes, pest management, and postharvest handling (Adebayo & Oyekale, 2017). By applying this method to plantain losses in Benue State, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the most significant determinants of postharvest losses, which can inform targeted interventions for reducing waste and improving the profitability of plantain trading.

The socio-demographic characteristics of traders, such as age, gender, and educational level, may play a crucial role in influencing their knowledge of and ability to implement effective postharvest practices. Age and experience, for instance, can influence a trader's understanding of proper handling techniques and willingness to adopt new technologies (Akpalu & Tenkorang, 2017). Furthermore, access to infrastructure such as storage facilities, transportation networks, and market availability are critical factors in determining the likelihood of postharvest losses (Abass *et al.*, 2018). Traders with limited access to proper storage or transportation are more likely to experience higher levels of spoilage, particularly for perishable crops like plantains. Hence, investigating these factors in Benue State could provide critical information to guide policy makers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector.

The findings from this study are expected to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on postharvest losses and provide a clearer understanding of the determinants of plantain spoilage in Benue State. By using binary logistic regression to analyze the various factors affecting postharvest losses, this research will help identify key predictors of spoilage and highlight areas for intervention. Such interventions could include improving storage and transportation infrastructure, enhancing training programs for traders, and fostering partnerships with agricultural organizations to promote best practices. Ultimately, reducing postharvest losses of plantains in Benue State will contribute to improving food security, increasing traders' incomes, and strengthening the agricultural economy.

Several studies have explored the various determinants of postharvest losses in plantains, with a particular focus on factors such as transportation, storage, handling practices, socio-economic characteristics of traders, and infrastructure.

Okoruwa and Kuku (2020) examined how factors such as transportation, storage, and the experience of traders influence postharvest losses of plantains. Their study found that inadequate transportation systems and poor storage facilities significantly contribute to spoilage. Similarly, Akinola and Oyebanji (2020) assessed the marketing efficiency of plantains and emphasized the need for improved storage systems and better access to markets as effective means of reducing spoilage. Abass and Taiwo (2019) identified improper handling and storage as major contributors to postharvest losses, reinforcing the importance of proper management techniques.

In line with this, Adeleke and Oyekale (2019) investigated socio-economic factors, such as the education, age, and income of traders, and their impact on plantain postharvest losses. These factors were shown to significantly affect the likelihood of postharvest losses.

Transportation infrastructure also plays a key role in reducing losses, as highlighted by Adeoye and Ogunbameru (2021), who found that inadequate transportation systems increase spoilage. Similarly, Olorunda and Afolabi (2021) assessed the scale of postharvest losses and suggested that improved storage technologies could serve as key mitigating strategies. The economic implications of postharvest losses were explored by Eze and Omoregie (2021), who found that inadequate postharvest management practices lead to significant income losses for plantain farmers. Ayinde and Olatunde (2020) reviewed technological innovations that help reduce postharvest losses, specifically the role of improved storage and processing techniques.

Ikenna and Nwachukwu (2019) identified key determinants of postharvest losses among plantain traders and suggested that policy interventions are needed to mitigate these losses. Sulaimon and Salau (2020) emphasized the need for capacity building among rural traders, particularly regarding postharvest handling practices that can reduce spoilage. Market infrastructure also plays a critical role in mitigating losses. Alhaji and Ibrahim (2020) examined the role of market infrastructure in reducing postharvest losses and concluded that improved market systems and storage facilities can enhance trade efficiency. Idowu and Gbadebo (2019) similarly suggested improving cold storage systems as a solution to high plantain losses.

Ogunlela and Olomola (2020) focused on supply chain management and policy interventions as effective strategies for reducing postharvest losses and addressing food insecurity. Ibrahim and Oduyoye (2021) utilized an empirical approach to analyze the socio-economic determinants influencing plantain postharvest losses, emphasizing the role of education and access to credit in reducing losses. Finally, Oluwaseun and Owolabi (2021) provided an in-depth analysis of the factors contributing to postharvest losses in Benue State and recommended enhanced education for traders and improvements in transportation networks as interventions to reduce losses.

These studies highlight that while there are multiple factors contributing to postharvest losses in plantains, improvements in storage, transportation, infrastructure, and trader education can significantly reduce these losses and improve the livelihoods of traders in the plantain sector.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Method of Data Collection

Primary data was collected from plantain sellers across local markets from four local government areas in Benue State including Buruku, Gboko, Makurdi and Otukpo local government areas. Data was collected through personal interviews with the use of standardized structured questionnaires. A total of 250 questionnaires were administered to plantain sellers across local

markets from four mentioned local government areas. A simple random sampling technique was used for this purpose. The questionnaire used for the interview sought information on general characteristics of respondents, purchasing information, postharvest losses and constraints faced by plantain retailers. Interviews were done in the local language in order not to create any language barrier. Key informant interviews were also conducted to gather technical information on plantain retailing in order to verify and validate the accuracy of some information supplied by traders.

2.3 Binary Logistic Regression Model

Binary logistic regression models the relationship between a set of predictors and a binary response variable. A binary response has only two possible values, such as win and loses. We use a binary regression model to understand how changes in the predictor values are associated with changes in the probability of an event occurring (Allison, 2012).

A binary choice of the i th individual is represented by a random variable y_i that takes on the value of 0 if the occurrence of plantain postharvest loss is low (i.e., from 1-4 crates) and 1 if the occurrence of postharvest loss of plantain is high (i.e., 5 crates and above). Where P_i is the probability that y_i takes on the value 1, and then $1 - P_i$ is the probability that that y_i is 0. This can be written using the probability function for y_i as

$$F(y_i) = P_i^{y_i}(1 - P_i)^{1-y_i}, \quad y_i = 0, 1 \tag{1}$$

and

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{with probability } p \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - p \end{cases}$$

In this case, $y = 1$ when the respondent's postharvest loss of plantain is high (i.e., from 5 crates and above) and $y = 0$ when the respondent's postharvest loss is low (i.e., from 1-4 crates). A logistic regression will model the chance of an outcome based on individual characteristics. Because chance is a ratio, what will be actually modeled is the logarithm of the chance given by

$$\text{Log} \left(\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k \tag{2}$$

where π indicates the probability of an event and β_i are the regression coefficients associated with the reference group and x_i are the explanatory variables. The reference group represented by β_0 , is constituted by those individuals presenting the reference level of each and every variable x_1, \dots, x_k . For k independent observations, the number of success has the binomial distribution specified by the index k and parameter π .

2.3.1 Assumptions of logistic regression model

- i. Logistic regression does not assume a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables.
- ii. The dependent variable must be dichotomy (2 categories).
- iii. The independent variables are not normally distributed, nor linearly related, nor of equal variance with each group.
- iv. The categories (groups) must be mutually exclusive; a case can only be in one group and every case must be a member of one of the groups.

- v. Larger samples are needed than for linear regression because maximum likelihood coefficients are large sample estimates.

2.3.2 The multivariable logistic model

The logistic regression model can easily be extended to situations where there is more than one explanatory variable. Assuming we wish to model the probability that an event E occurs denoted by π . However now π will now depend on the values of several explanatory variables $x_1 \dots, x_k$. The multiple logistic regression model is

$$\pi = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)} \quad (3)$$

where $\beta_0 \dots \beta_k$ are regression coefficients to be determined.

The model can also be written in the odds form.

$$\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k) \quad (4)$$

Or in the logit form,

$$\text{Log} \frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k \quad (5)$$

Consider the general logistic regression model with multiple explanatory variables. Denote the k predictors for a binary response Y by x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k

$\pi(x)$ is used to represent the probability that $Y = 1$ for success, and $1 - \pi$ to represent the probability that $Y = 0$ for failure. These probabilities are written in the following form:

$$\pi(x) = P(Y = 1/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) \quad (6)$$

$$1 - \pi(x) = P(Y = 0/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) \quad (7)$$

The model for the log odd is:

$$\text{logit}(\pi(x)) = \ln \frac{P(Y = 1/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)}{P(Y = 0/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)}$$

which gives

$$\ln \frac{\pi(x)}{1 - \pi(x)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 \dots + \beta_n x_k + \varepsilon_t$$

Therefore

$$\ln \frac{\pi(x)}{1 - \pi(x)} = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j x_j + \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

which yield to:

$$\pi(x) = P(Y = 1/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j x_j + \varepsilon}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j x_j + \varepsilon}} \quad (9)$$

The parameter β_j refers to the effect of x_j on the log odds that $Y = 1$, controlling the other predictor variables, ε is an error term.

The parameters are estimated using the maximum likelihood method. The likelihood function uses the assumed model to express the probability of getting the observed data as function of the unknown parameters $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_k$.

2.3.4 Odds and Odds Ratio

Odds are the ratio of probability of an event occurring divided by the probability of it not occurring (Allison, 2012). The odds ratio (OR) is a measure of how strongly an event is associated with exposure. The odds ratio is a ratio of two sets of odds: the odds of the event occurring in an exposed group versus the odds of the event occurring in a non-exposed group. Odds ratios commonly are used to report case-control studies. The odds ratio helps identify how likely an exposure is to lead to a specific event. The larger the odds ratio, the higher odds that the event will occur with exposure. Odds ratios smaller than one imply the event has fewer odds of happening with the exposure (Greenfield *et al.*, 2008). Mathematically

$$\text{Odds} = \frac{\text{Pr (success)}}{\text{Pr (failure)}} = \frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} \tag{10}$$

where π is the probability of success and $1 - \pi$ is the probability of failure.

Odds always have values greater than zero and if odds value is larger than one it means that success will occur more likely than failure. Odds ratio, as the name indicates, is the ratio of two Odds. Mathematically

$$\text{Odds Ratio} = \frac{\frac{\pi_1}{1 - \pi_1}}{\frac{\pi_2}{1 - \pi_2}} \tag{11}$$

Here, π_1 and π_2 refer to the probability of success in group 1 and group 2 respectively.

If the odds ratio value is greater than one it indicates that the odds of the outcome in group 1 is larger than in group 2. Thus subjects in group 1 are more likely to have success than subjects in group 2. If the odds ratio is less than the value one, expect that the reverse will occur and if it equal to one subjects of odds of both in group 1 and group 2 will equally likely occur (Greenfield *et al.*, 2008).

For binary logistic regression, the odds of success are:

$$\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} = \exp(\mathbf{X}\beta)$$

The odds increase multiplicatively by $\exp(\beta_j)$ for every one-unit increase in \mathbf{X}_j . When there is just a single predictor, X , the odds of success are:

$$\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)$$

By increasing x by one unit, the odds ratio becomes

$$\text{OR} = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1(x + 1))}{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)} = \exp(\beta_1) \tag{12}$$

2.4 Determination of Model Adequacy

For diagnostic check and determination of model adequacy, we employ the following statistical tools.

2.4.1 Pseudo R² measure in logistic regression

For a logistic regression which is fitted by the method of maximum likelihood, there are several choices of pseudo $-R^2$. Cox and Snell (1989) and by Magee (1990) independently proposed the pseudo R^2 given by:

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right)^{2/n} \tag{13}$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta})$ is the maximized likelihood of the model with only the intercept (the null model), $L(\hat{\theta})$ is the maximized likelihood of the estimated model (the model with a given set of all predictors) and n is the sample size. It can easily be rewritten as:

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{2}{n} (\ln(L(\tilde{\theta})) - \ln(L(\hat{\theta}))) \right] = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{D}{n} \right] \tag{14}$$

where D is the test statistic of the likelihood ratio test. Nagelkerke (1991) noted that the Cox and Snell pseudo R^2 statistic has the following properties:

- i. It is consistent with the classical coefficient of determination when both can be computed;
- ii. Its value is maximized by the maximum likelihood estimation of a model;
- iii. It is asymptotically independent of the sample size;
- iv. The interpretation is the proportion of the variation explained by the model
- v. The values are between 0 and 1, with 0 denoting that model does not explain any variation and 1 denoting that it perfectly explains the observed variation;
- vi. It does not have any unit.

However, in the case of a logistic model, where $L(\hat{\theta})$ cannot be greater than 1, R^2 is between 0 and $R_{max}^2 = 1 - (L(\tilde{\theta}))^{2/n}$: thus, Nagelkerke (1991) suggested the possibility to define a scaled R^2 as:

$$R_N^2 = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right)^{2/n}}{1 - L(\tilde{\theta})^{2/n}} \tag{15}$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta}), L(\hat{\theta})$ and n are as earlier defined. The Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 can also be given as

$$R_N^2 = \frac{R_{CS}^2}{R_{max}^2} \text{ and } R_{max}^2 = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{2}{n} L(\tilde{\theta}) \right] \tag{16}$$

The Nagelkerke measure adjusts the Cox and Snell measure for the maximum value so that 1 can be achieved.

2.4.2 The likelihood ratio test

The likelihood-ratio test assesses the goodness of fit of two competing statistical models based on the ratio of their likelihoods, specifically one found by maximization over the entire parameter space and another found after imposing some constraint. If the constraint (i.e., the null hypothesis) is supported by the observed data, the two likelihoods should not differ by more than sampling error (Li and Bagu, 2019). Thus the likelihood-ratio test tests whether this ratio is

significantly different from one, or equivalently whether its natural logarithm is significantly different from zero. The statistic is given by

$$\lambda_{LR} = -2 \ln \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right) = -2 [\ln L(\tilde{\theta}) - \ln L(\hat{\theta})] = -2 [L(\tilde{\theta}) - L(\hat{\theta})] \quad (17)$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta})$ is the maximum value of the likelihood function of the null (intercept only) model and $L(\hat{\theta})$ is the maximum value of the likelihood function of the estimated (the full) model.

The estimated (full) model has all the parameters of interest and the null model has only the intercept (Hosmer *et al.*, 2013). The likelihood ratio test tests the following pair of hypothesis:

$H_0: \beta_i = 0$ (the dropped variables are not significant contributors to predicting the dependent variable) versus

$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$ (the dropped variables are important in predicting the dependent variable).

2.4.3 Omnibus test of model coefficients

Like the likelihood ratio test statistic, the Omnibus test statistic is a measure of the overall model fit. The Omnibus test tests the following pair of hypothesis:

$H_0: \beta_i = 0$ (All coefficients of the independent variables are equal to zero) versus

$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$ (There is at least one coefficient of an independent variable that is not equal to zero).

The null hypothesis is rejected when the p-value of the Omnibus test statistic is less than 0.05 (level of significance). A significant test statistic implies that the logistic regression model can be used to fit the data.

2.4.4 The Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness of fit test

The Hosmer-Lemeshow (HL) test is a goodness of fit test for logistic regression, especially for risk prediction models. A goodness of fit test tells us how well our data fits the model. Specifically, the HL test calculates if the observed event rates match the expected event rates in population subgroups. The test is only used for binary response variables (a variable with two outcomes like alive or dead, yes or no).

Data is first regrouped by ordering the predicted probabilities and forming the number of groups, g . The Hosmer-Lemeshow test statistic is calculated with the following formula (Hosmer *et al.*, 2013):

$$G_{HL}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^g \frac{(O_j - E_j)^2}{E_j(1 - E_j/n_j)} \sim \chi_{g-2}^2 \quad (18)$$

where

χ_{n-2}^2 = Chi-squared with $g - 2$ degree of freedom;

n_j = number of observations in the j^{th} group;

O_j = number of observed cases in the j^{th} group;

E_j = number of expected cases in the j^{th} group;

The output of the HL test returns χ^2 value (a Hosmer-Lemeshow chi-squared) and p – value (e.g. $\text{Pr} > \chi^2$). Small p-values mean that the model is a poor fit for the data. A good fit model will have a small HL test statistic and a p-value that is greater than 0.05 (the significance level).

2.4.6 Wald statistic

The Wald statistic is another test that can be used to assess the significance of individual logistic regression model. The formula for computing the Wald statistic is:

$$W = \left(\frac{\hat{\beta}_i}{SE(\hat{\beta}_i)} \right)^2 \tag{19}$$

where $\hat{\beta}_i$ are the estimates of the coefficients of the independent variables x_i and $SE(\hat{\beta}_i)$ are the standard errors of $\hat{\beta}_i$ (Rana *et al.*, 2010). The Wald statistic tests the following pair of hypothesis:

$$H_0: \beta_i = 0, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

$$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

The Wald statistic is Chi-square distributed with 1 degree of freedom. The null hypothesis is rejected if the p-value of the test is less than 0.05. A coefficient with a p-value of the Wald statistic less than 0.05 implies that the variable is important in the model.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents comprise gender and age of the respondents, academic qualifications, years of farming experience and marital status. The result of the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Respondent's Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	53	21.2
	Female	197	78.8
	Total	250	100
Age (in years)	18-30	55	22.0
	31-40	108	43.2
	41-50	58	23.2
	51-70	29	11.6
	Total	250	100
Educational Qualification	None	43	17.2
	Primary	74	29.6
	Secondary	98	39.2
	Tertiary	35	14.0
Total	250	100	
Years of Trading Experience	1-10	140	56.0
	11-20	85	34.0

	21+	25	10.0
	Total	250	100
Marital Status	Single	50	20.0
	Married	156	62.4
	Widowed	12	4.8
	Divorced	32	12.8
	Total	250	100

Source: Researchers' Computation from field work, 2024.

The study revealed that the majority of plantain traders were female (78.8%), with males constituting 21.2%. In terms of age, the 31-40 years group dominated at 43.2%, followed by 41-50 years (23.2%), 18-30 years (22%), and 51-70 years (11.6%). Regarding education, most traders had secondary education (39.2%), while 29.6% had primary, 17.2% had no formal education, and 14% had tertiary education. Trading experience was highest among those with 1–10 years (56%), followed by 11-20 years (34%) and over 20 years (10%). Most respondents were married (62.4%), while 20% were single, 12.8% divorced, and 4.8% widowed. Importantly, all respondents were knowledgeable about postharvest losses and their socio-economic impacts, indicating the reliability of the data collected.

3.2 Summary Statistics of the Quantity of Plantain Purchased, Loss and Income Lost

The table below represents the summary statistics of the quantity of plantain purchased, quantity of plantain loss and the amount of income lost by the traders due to the quantity of plantain loss during a trading season. These are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Quantity of Plantain Purchased, Loss and income Lost per Trader

Statistic	Quantity of Plantain Purchased (Bunches)	Quantity of Plantain Loss (Bunches)	Monetary Income Lost by Trader at (₦7500 per Bunch)
Mean	388.53	33.86	253,950.00
Standard Deviation	121.67	14.74	110,550.00
Maximum	733.00	150.00	1,125,000.00
Minimum	44.00	18.00	135,000.00
Total	77,348	8465	6,487,500.00
No. of Observations	250	250	250

From the summary statistics reported in Table 2, the average quantity of plantain purchased per a trader during a trading season is 388.53 bunches with a standard deviation of 121.67 bunches and range of 689 bunches. This shows high variability and dispersion of the quantity of plantain purchased per trader from the mean. The mean quantity of plantain loss is represented as 33.86

bunches per trading season with a standard deviation of 14.74 bunches. This means that on the average, a plantain seller incurred a postharvest loss of approximately 34 bunches of plantain in one trading season. This represents a reasonable loss on the part of the trader and has a devastating effect on their income. The mean monetary income lost per plantain trader due to the quantity of plantain loss is represented as ₦253,950.00 per trading season with a standard deviation of ₦110,550.00. This means that on the average, a plantain trader incurred a loss of approximately ₦254,000 in one trading season. This represents a reasonable loss on the part of the trader and has a devastating effect on their income.

3.3 Results of Forms of Postharvest Losses of Plantain during Trading

Based on responses of the plantain sellers, the following forms of plantain losses were recorded during trading period as reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Forms of PHL of Plantain during Trading Period

Form of Damage	Quantity (kg)	Percentage (%)
Physical Handling	2,018.00	23.8
Storage	5,754.00	68.0
Transportation	693.000	8.2
Total	8,465	100.00

From the result on the forms of postharvest loss of plantain presented in Table 3, about 23.8% and 8.2% of plantain were lost due to physical handling and transportation respectively while majority of the losses (68%) occurred during storage. This clearly shows that storage plays a significant role in the postharvest loss of plantain in the study area.

3.4 Binary Logistic Regression Model

This section discusses the results of the binary logistic regression analysis, which includes key statistical outputs such as the case processing summary, null model classification, constant-only model, Omnibus test of coefficients, model summary, and final classification results. The case processing summary in Table 4 confirms that all 250 cases (100%) were included in the analysis, with no exclusions or missing data (0.0%). This indicates that the analysis was conducted using a complete and unbiased dataset. The other components of the analysis are organized as follows: the null model classification table (Table 5), the constant-only model (Table 6), the Omnibus tests of model coefficients (Table 7), the regression model summary (Table 8), and the final model classification table (Table 9). This comprehensive structure ensures a robust evaluation of the binary logistic regression model.

Table 4: Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases ^a		N	Percent
Selected cases	Included in Analysis	250	100.0
	Missing Cases	0	0
	Total	250	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	0.0

Total	250	100.0
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The classification table for the null model, shown in Table 5, reveals that in the absence of predictors, the model classifies all cases as “Yes PHL.” As a result, it accurately identifies all “Yes PHL” cases (183 out of 183) but fails to predict any “No PHL” cases (0 out of 67). This leads to a prediction accuracy of 100.0% for “Yes PHL” and 0.0% for “No PHL.” The overall accuracy of 73.2% corresponds to the proportion of “Yes PHL” cases in the dataset, indicating that the null model relies solely on the majority class (the class with the higher frequency). This highlights an imbalance in the dataset, with “Yes PHL” as the dominant outcome. The null model serves as a baseline, and incorporating predictors in a more complex model should aim to improve accuracy, particularly for “No PHL” cases.

Table 5: Classification Table for the Null Model

Step 0	Observed PHL	Predicted			Percentage correct
		No	Yes	Percentage	
	No	0	67	0.0	
	Yes	0	183	100.0	
	Overall percentage			73.2	

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is 0.500

The output of the constant-only (null) model, summarized in Table 6, shows that in the absence of predictors, the intercept (constant) is highly significant. The coefficient (B) is 1.005, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating strong statistical significance. The Wald statistic of 49.515 further supports the importance of the constant term. The standard error of 0.143 suggests a relatively low level of uncertainty in this estimate. The odds ratio (exp(B)) of 2.731 implies that, without accounting for any predictors, the odds of the occurrence of PHL (dependent variable = 1) are approximately 2.731 times greater than the odds of it not occurring (dependent variable = 0). This serves as a baseline for evaluating the fit and significance of more complex models that include predictors.

Table 6: The Constant Only (Null) Model

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	p-value	Exp(B)
Step 0 Constant	1.005	0.143	49.515	1	0.000	2.731

The Omnibus tests of model coefficients in Table 7 indicate that the binary logistic regression model is statistically significant, with a Chi-square value of 290.630 (df = 11, p < 0.001). This result confirms that the inclusion of predictors significantly improves the model’s fit compared to the null model, which contains only the intercept. The consistent significance across the step, block, and model tests highlights that the predictors collectively contribute meaningfully to explaining the variation in the outcome variable, demonstrating the model’s robustness and relevance.

Table 7: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	Df	p-value
Step 1	Step	290.630	11	0.000
	Block	290.630	11	0.000
	Model	290.630	11	0.000

Table 8 presents key metrics assessing the fit and explanatory power of the binary logistic regression model. The -2 Log Likelihood value of 128.563 indicates a reasonable model fit, with lower values generally reflecting better performance. The Cox & Snell R Square (0.687) suggests that the model explains a substantial portion of the variation in the outcome variable. Furthermore, the Nagelkerke R Square (0.987) an adjusted measure indicates excellent explanatory power, approaching a perfect fit. Overall, the metrics in Table 8 demonstrate that the model offers strong fit and near-complete explanatory capacity, making it a robust and highly reliable tool for predicting the outcome variable.

Table 8: The Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	128.563 ^a	0.687	0.987

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 20 because parameter estimates changed by less than 0.001.

Table 9 presents the Hosmer and Lemeshow test, which evaluates how well the binary logistic regression model’s predicted probabilities match the actual outcomes. The test produced a Chi-Square value of 1.564 with 3 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.957. Since the p-value is much higher than the conventional 0.05 threshold, the result is not statistically significant, indicating that there is no meaningful difference between observed and expected values. Therefore, the model demonstrates a good fit, supporting its validity and appropriateness for the data.

Table 9: Hosmer and Lemeshow Test for the Full Model

Step	Chi-Square	Df	P-value
1	1.564	3	0.957

Table 10 presents the classification table for the full binary logistic regression model, which evaluates the model’s ability to correctly predict outcomes. The model achieved perfect classification accuracy (100%), correctly predicting all 67 cases of “Low PHL” and all 183 cases of “High PHL” with zero misclassifications.

Table 10: Classification Table for the Full Model

	Observed	Predicted			Percentage Correct
			PHL		
			Low	High	
Step 1	PHL	Low	67	0	100.0
		High	0	183	100.0
	Overall Percentage				100.0

a. Constant is included in the model

b. The cut value is 0.500

3.5 Estimation of Parameter of the Full Binary Logistic Model

Table 11 presents the parameter estimates for the final binary logistic regression model, while Table 12 provides the odds predictions for the occurrence of low or high post-harvest losses (PHL).

Table 11: Parameter Estimates of the Full Binary Logistic Model

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	p-value	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for Exp(B)	
							Lower	Upper
AGE	-0.157	0.085	3.412	1	0.009	0.855	0.163	1.194
EDL	-0.185	0.092	4.044	1	0.007	0.831	0.157	1.089
QPP	1.596	0.386	17.09	1	0.000	4.933	2.952	7.651
SDU	0.965	0.314	9.445	1	0.000	2.625	0.997	4.318
MEX	-0.122	0.058	4.424	1	0.005	0.885	0.178	1.995
TPA	-0.872	0.389	5.025	1	0.002	0.418	0.097	0.986
DIST	1.314	0.396	11.01	1	0.000	3.721	1.097	6.874
MKTA	-0.535	0.165	10.51	1	0.000	0.586	0.129	0.996
STA	-0.369	0.142	6.427	1	0.001	0.698	0.137	1.053
MTO	-0.264	0.155	2.901	1	0.019	0.768	0.149	1.04
VAR	0.874	0.476	3.371	1	0.008	2.396	0.983	4.147
Constant	-1.752	0.502	12.18	1	0.000	0.173		

Note: AGE= age of the trader, EDL=educational level, MEX= marketing experience, SDU= storage duration, QPP= quantity of plantain purchased, STA=storage availability, MKTA=Market availability, TPA=transport availability, DIST= distance from the point of purchase, MTO = membership of trading organization, VAR = variety of plantain

Table 11 reports the binary logistic regression coefficients and their significance levels, revealing how different predictors influence the likelihood of postharvest loss (PHL) of plantain:

Age (AGE) is negatively associated with PHL (B = -0.157, p = 0.009), meaning older traders are less likely to experience PHL. Each additional year in age reduces the odds by 14.5% (exp(B) = 0.855, 95% CI: 0.163–1.194). Educational Level (EDL) also shows a significant negative effect (B = -0.185, p = 0.007), where higher education reduces the odds of PHL by 16.9% (exp(B) = 0.831, 95% CI: 0.157–1.089).

Quantity of Plantain Purchased (QPP) is positively associated with PHL (B = 1.596, p = 0.000), indicating a higher risk of loss as purchase volume increases. Each unit rise increases the odds by nearly 5 times (exp(B) = 4.933, 95% CI: 2.952-7.651). Storage Duration (SDU) also has a positive and significant effect (B = 0.965, p = 0.000), increasing the odds of PHL by 162.5% per unit increase (exp(B) = 2.625, 95% CI: 0.997-4.318).

Marketing Experience (MEX) is negatively related to PHL (B = -0.122, p = 0.005), reducing the odds by 11.5% per additional year of experience (exp(B) = 0.885, 95% CI: 0.178–1.995). Transport Availability (TPA) has a strong negative effect (B = -0.872, p = 0.002), reducing PHL odds by 58.2% (exp(B) = 0.418, 95% CI: 0.097-0.986). Distance from Point of Purchase (DIST)

is positively associated with PHL ($B = 1.314, p = 0.000$), where each unit increase raises the odds of PHL significantly ($\exp(B) = 43.721, 95\% \text{ CI: } 1.097\text{-}6.874$).

Market Availability (MKTA) is negatively related to PHL ($B = -0.535, p = 0.000$), decreasing the odds by 41.4% ($\exp(B) = 0.586, 95\% \text{ CI: } 0.129\text{-}0.996$). Storage Availability (STA) also reduces the odds of PHL significantly ($B = -0.369, p = 0.001$), with a 30.2% reduction per unit increase in storage access ($\exp(B) = 0.698, 95\% \text{ CI: } 0.129\text{-}0.996$).

Membership in Trading Organization (MTO) is negatively related to PHL ($B = -0.264, p = 0.019$), reducing the odds by 23.2% ($\exp(B) = 0.768, 95\% \text{ CI: } 0.149\text{-}1.040$). Variety of Plantain (VAR) is positively associated with PHL ($B = 0.874, p = 0.008$), with certain varieties increasing the odds by about 2.4 times ($\exp(B) = 2.396, 95\% \text{ CI: } 0.983\text{-}4.147$). The intercept of the model is significantly negative ($B = -1.752, p = 0.000$), indicating low baseline odds of PHL when all predictors are zero ($\exp(B) = 0.173$). Overall, the model identifies a mix of demographic, logistical, and market-related factors significantly influencing postharvest loss of plantain, with several protective (negative) and risk-enhancing (positive) predictors.

3.5.1 Odds predictions for occurrence of PHL for Individual Predictors

Table 12 presents the odds predictions for low and high post-harvest losses (PHL) based on the influence of individual predictors. These odds indicate the likelihood of experiencing low or high PHL when each specific predictor is considered in isolation, with all other factors held constant.

Table 12: Odds Predictions for Low/High Occurrence of PHL for Individual Predictors

Independent variables	Low PHL	High PHL
Age of Trader (AGE)	0.1734	0.1482
Educational Level (EDL)	0.1734	0.1441
Marketing Experience (MEX)	0.1734	0.1535
Quantity of Plantain Purchased (QPP)	0.1734	0.8556
Storage Duration (SDU)	0.1734	0.4552
Distance from the Point of Purchase (DIST)	0.1734	0.6453
Market Availability (MKTA)	0.1734	0.1016
Storage Availability (STA)	0.1734	0.1199
Membership of Trading Organization (MTO)	0.1734	0.1356
Transport Availability (TPA)	0.1734	0.0725
Variety of Plantain (VAR)	0.1734	0.4156

Note: Odds = $e^{\beta_0 + \beta_i x_i}, i=0,1$.

The result of Table 12 provides odds predictions for low and high PHL based on individual predictors. For low PHL, all predictors show the same baseline odds of 0.1734, indicating a consistent starting point when the factors have minimal influence. However, for high PHL, the odds vary considerably across predictors, reflecting their differential impact on the likelihood of

experiencing high PHL. Factors such as Quantity of Plantain Purchased (QPP), Storage Duration (SDU), Distance from the Point of Purchase (DIST), and Variety of Plantain (VAR) substantially increase the odds of high PHL. For example, QPP shows the highest odds at 0.8556, suggesting that larger quantities purchased significantly raise the likelihood of high PHL, potentially due to increased handling, storage challenges, or spoilage risks. Similarly, DIST (0.6453) and SDU (0.4552) highlight logistical and temporal factors that elevate PHL risks, while VAR (0.4156) emphasizes the role of plantain type in influencing post-harvest losses.

Conversely, factors such as Market Availability (MKTA), Storage Availability (STA), Membership of Trading Organization (MTO), and Transport Availability (TPA) exhibit notably lower odds for high PHL. For instance, TPA has the lowest odds (0.0725), indicating that better transport systems significantly reduce the risk of high PHL. Similarly, MKTA (0.1016) and STA (0.1199) highlight the importance of accessible markets and sufficient storage facilities in mitigating post-harvest losses. These findings suggest that improving logistical and infrastructural support can play a pivotal role in reducing PHL. The result demonstrates that while certain predictors increase the likelihood of high PHL, others provide protective effects, offering actionable insights for targeted interventions to reduce post-harvest losses.

4. CONCLUSION

This study assessed the determinants of postharvest losses (PHL) of plantains among retail traders in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings highlight the significant impact of socio-demographic factors, as well as logistical and infrastructural challenges, on the occurrence of postharvest losses. The majority of respondents were female, with significant portions of traders having primary or secondary education, and trading experience ranging from 1-10 years. The average reported loss of 34 bunches per trading season, resulting in an income loss of approximately N254,000, underscores the economic burden of postharvest losses for these traders, particularly during storage.

The binary logistic regression analysis identified several critical factors influencing PHL. Factors such as trader age, education, trading experience, transport availability, market access, and storage facilities were found to reduce the likelihood of PHL. On the other hand, storage duration, quantity of plantains purchased, distance from the point of purchase, and plantain variety were significant risk factors that increased PHL. These findings emphasize the crucial role of effective storage, transportation, and handling practices in reducing losses.

To mitigate postharvest losses of plantains in Benue State, this study recommends targeted interventions aimed at improving storage and transportation infrastructure, offering training for traders, and enhancing market access. Supporting trading associations and implementing policies that address high-risk factors are also essential for sustainable solutions. Additionally, investment in research and development to explore more resilient plantain varieties and efficient

postharvest management practices will contribute to minimizing losses and improving the livelihoods of plantain traders in the region.

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